

UZBEKISTAN STATE UNIVERSITY OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION SPORT
PLANNING OF PARTIKAL TRAYNING HIGHLY QUALIFIED ATHLETES
WITH MUSCULOSKELETAL INJURIES

Abdiev Sherzod Abdurakhmonovich

Utashev Khasan Nematillayevich

Dehqonov Ravshan Karim o'g'li

Gareyeva Gulchehra Renatovna

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7486253>

Abstract. This article discusses the issues of planning competitive loads of highly qualified athletes with basic strength training and technical training of highly qualified paraathletes, achievements in international competitions.

Keyword: Athletes with defects of the musculoskeletal system, special physical training, General recovery, the number and indicators of the training process.

УЗБЕКСКИЙ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО
ВОСПИТАНИЯ СПОРТА ПЛАНИРОВАНИЕ ПАРТНЕРСКИХ ТРЕНИРОВОК
ВЫСОКОКВАЛИФИЦИРОВАННЫХ СПОРТСМЕНОВ С ТРАВМАМИ ОПОРНО-
МЫШЕЧНОГО КОЛЕСА

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы планирования соревновательных нагрузок спортсменов высокой квалификации при базовой силовой подготовке и технической подготовке параспортсменов

в высокой квалификации, достижения на международных соревнованиях.

Ключевое слово: Спортсмены с дефектами опорно-двигательного аппарата, специальная физическая подготовка, общее восстановление, количество и показатели тренировочного процесса.

Introduction. Paralympic sport at the present stage is characterized by a constant increase in competition with a high density and a high level of results, which places special demands on the training of athletes participating in responsible international competitions. The central event of adaptive sports is the Paralympic Games, which were first held in Rome (Italy) in 1960. Paralympic sport was recognized in our country at the end of the 20th century. Athletes with musculoskeletal disorders from our country took part in the Paralympic Games for the first time in 2004. Athletics with a musculoskeletal injury is the most medal-intensive event, on which the team standings at the Summer Paralympic Games depend to the greatest extent. In 2016, 7 sets of medals were played in paraathletic disciplines. [8,18,28,38,48,58,68,78,88,98]

At present, much attention is paid to the development of adaptive sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan. With the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-2821 dated March 9, 2017 "Preparation of Uzbek athletes for the XXXII Summer Olympic Games in 2020 and for the XVI Paralympic Games in Tokyo 2020". To date, Paralympic athletes of our country have won 16 licenses, of which 9 belong to Paralympic athletes. Competitive exercises, as well as the content of sports training in the disciplines of athletics, to a large extent differ from the paraathletics of people with a lesion of the musculoskeletal system. Because of these differences, it is inappropriate to copy the content, volume and intensity of sports training. For effective training of athletes in the disciplines of track and field athletics of the sport of people with lesions of the musculoskeletal system, it is necessary to create a system of sports training that takes into account all the features of training and competitive activities, as well as the contingent of those involved. [1,11,21,31,41,51,61,71,81,91]

We have found that there is not enough empirical and theoretical data in the scientific literature to create a scientifically based system of sports training for highly qualified athletes with lesions of the musculoskeletal system. The most acute situation was revealed in the disciplines performed by athletes in a sitting position, as well as in the disciplines performed

using prosthetic equipment. However, we have not found any works on studying the types of sports training in most of the studied disciplines - technical, tactical, physical, as well as periodization of training and control systems. Purpose of the study. [3,13,23,33,43,53,63,73,83,93] To develop theoretically and experimentally substantiate the planning of sports training for highly qualified Paralympic athletes, taking into account the peculiarities of training and competitive activity.

Subject of study. Planning of sports training of highly qualified athletes specializing in the disciplines of track and field athletics of the sport of persons with lesions of the musculoskeletal system. Hypothesis. It was assumed that the increase in the effectiveness of training and competitive activities of highly qualified athletes with lesions of the musculoskeletal system in the disciplines of athletics can be achieved through the use of a system of sports training, which is based on: - implementation, when choosing means and methods of preparation, of the principles of accounting and leveling of nosological features (the principle of identifying and accounting for the possibilities of performing movements, the principle of constant modernization and maximum use of special technical means); - optimization of the types of sports training - physical, technical, technical and design, based on the accentuated development of special physical qualities to which an athlete is genetically predisposed, taking into account the specifics of competitive activity, as well as the features of the material and technical base - the presence of special prosthetic equipment, running wheelchairs, throwing machines. [4,14,24,34,44,54,64,74,84,94]

To achieve this goal and confirm the proposed hypothesis, the following research objectives were identified. 1) based on the analysis of special literature and practical experience, to identify the components necessary for planning and building sports training in the disciplines of athletics of the sport of people with lesions of the musculoskeletal system; 2) to identify the features of the training and competitive activity of highly qualified athletes in the disciplines of athletics of the sport of persons with lesions of the musculoskeletal system; Scientific novelty of the research results. The system of sports training of highly qualified athletes in the disciplines of track and field athletics of the sport of persons with lesions of the musculoskeletal system was formed and experimentally substantiated, in which specific tasks were solved through the implementation of special principles of sports training, including the principles of accounting and leveling of nosological features, based on the use of means and methods of physical, technical, psychological, technical and design, tactical, theoretical, integral training; [2,12,22,32,42,52,62,72,82,92,]

When developing an experimental methodology to substantiate physical training in the athletics disciplines of the sport of people with musculoskeletal disorders, the planning of the training load was carried out at the basic stage lasting eight weeks - three shock weekly microcycles, one control-transitional weekly microcycle; then the training cycle was repeated. After the basic stage, the athletes performed the load of the pre-competitive stage of preparation, lasting six weeks - two shock weekly microcycles, one control-transitional weekly microcycle; then the training cycle was repeated. The experiment ended a week before the main start, in which the control-transitional microcycle was introduced. [6,16,26,36,46,56,66,76,86,96] During the implementation of the experimental methodology, each training session, due to the filling with certain means, had its own focus, a schematic distribution of which during the weekly microcycles at the basic stage and the stage of pre-competitive training for each athlete is shown in Figures 1 and 2. [9,19,29,39,49,59,69,79,89,99]

Distribution of training sessions with different directions in a shock weekly microcycle at the stage of precompetitive training for athletes of the first formative pedagogical experiment

When introducing an experimental methodology to substantiate physical training in the athletics disciplines of sports for people with musculoskeletal disorders at the basic stage, to solve the main tasks of sports training in training sessions, the following means and methods

were supposed to be used: - the amount of funds performed by the athlete K.A. during the experiment, they differed significantly in the values of the following groups of means - aerobic exercises, jumps with more than 10 repulsions; significantly lower values of the following groups of means - running up to 80 m (80-90%);

It was revealed that the set of special physical qualities in the disciplines of track and field athletics of the sport of people with musculoskeletal disorders of various sports and functional classes is identical, but the means and methods of developing these physical qualities can largely differ. On the basis of the principle of individualization of sports training, we conducted a pedagogical experiment to substantiate the physical training of highly qualified athletes in the disciplines of athletics of the sport of people with musculoskeletal disorders. The basis of this experiment was the accentuated development at the basic stage and at the stage of pre-competitive training of actual special physical qualities by increasing the volume of relatively safe means of their development. At the end of the experiment, there was an improvement in the results in pedagogical tests, characterizing the level of special physical fitness. [5,15,25,35,45,55,65,75,85,95,]

To assess the level of development of special physical qualities of athletes in the experimental group before and after the experiment, a battery of pedagogical tests was introduced, which is able to comprehensively assess this level. The test results are shown in tables 1 and 2. Table 1. [7,17,27,37,47,57,67,77,87,97] The results of pedagogical tests that assess the level of development of special physical qualities of athletes of the experimental group, before the second stage of the formative pedagogical experiment

Pedagogical tests	Athletes						M±m
	A.A.	K.A.	M.E.	F.B.	H.A.	B.M.	
Throwing the nucleus with two hands from behind the head, m*	11,53 (3 кг)	11,89 (2 кг)	8,21 (3 кг)	6,35 (2 кг)	8,12 (3 кг)	4,58 (2 кг)	8,45± 1,07
Throwing the nucleus with two hands from the chest, m *	12,82 (3 кг)	11,26 (2 кг)	9,23 (3 кг)	7,48 (2 кг)	9,04 (3 кг)	6,11 (2 кг)	9,32± 0,91
Throwing the ball 150 g with one hand, m *	63,68	52,41	47,23	41,94	46,20	30,12	46,93± 4,15
The bench press in the lying on the back in the "Smith Machine", equal to 70% of its own weight, 5 times a while, from	3,68	4,02	3,73	5,29	3,74	5,12	4,26± 0,28
Bending-extensions of hands in a hang on the crossbar 5 times a while, with	4,15	4,03	4,34	5,14	4,54	6,21	4,74± 0,31
The bench press in the lying on the back, kg	167,5	95	112,5	107,5	122,5	97,5	117,1± 9,94
* - The exercise is performed in a sitting position.							

Table 2. The results of pedagogical tests that assess the level of development of special physical qualities of athletes of the experimental group, after the second stage of the formative pedagogical experiment

Pedagogical tests	Athletes						M±m
	A.A.	K.A.	M.E.	F.B.	H.A.	B.M.	
Throwing the nucleus with two hands from behind the head, m*	11,28 (3 кґ)	12,05 (2 кґ)	8,42 (3 кґ)	6,17 (2 кґ)	8,51 (3 кґ)	4,24 (2 кґ)	8,45± 1,21
Throwing the nucleus with two hands from the chest, m *	13,24 (3 кґ)	10,58 (2 кґ)	9,83 (3 кґ)	7,68 (2 кґ)	8,74 (3 кґ)	5,97 (2 кґ)	9,34± 1,02
Throwing the ball 150 g with one hand, m *	61,93	53,37	45,02	42,26	46,23	31,36	46,7± 4,22
The bench press in the lying on the back in the "Smith Machine", equal to 70% of its own weight, 5 times a while, from	3,46	3,90	3,58	5,53	3,62	5,42	4,25± 0,39
Bending-extensions of hands in a hang on the crossbar 5 times a while, with	4,04	4,17	4,21	4,92	4,24	6,41	4,67± 0,37
The bench press in the lying on the back, kg	162,5	97,50	115	105	127,5	92,5	116,7± 10,5
* - The exercise is performed in a sitting position.							

When comparing the results of a battery of pedagogical tests that assess the level of development of special physical fitness before and after the pedagogical experiment, no significant differences were found (at $P < 0.05$) in any test. At the responsible competitions - the championship of Uzbekistan in athletics for persons with musculoskeletal disorders, the results of athletes improved when compared with official personal records: in the shot put ($n=5$) it was 10.25 ± 1.01 m, it became 11.03 ± 1.09 m, the average improvement was 0.78 m ($P < 0.05$), in discus throw ($n=2$) it was 29.06 ± 9.22 m, it became 31.13 ± 8.93 m, the average improvement was 2, 07 m ($P < 0.05$), in javelin throw ($n=5$) it was 23.20 ± 3.12 m, it became 24.27 ± 2.97 m, the average improvement was 1.06 m ($P < 0, 05$). At the Asian Championships in 2019, the athletes of the experimental group showed good results in 5 disciplines. Set 2 personal records in 4 disciplines.

The obtained results may indicate that in the course of the formative pedagogical experiment it was possible to increase the level of technical training in competitive exercises of highly qualified athletes with musculoskeletal disorders. Findings. As a result of the research, the planning of sports training for highly qualified athletes in the disciplines of athletics of the sport of people with lesions of the musculoskeletal system was experimentally substantiated. The ascertaining and forming pedagogical experiments were carried out in turn, which ensured the preparation of athletes for important competitions.

As a result of the main stage of the formative pedagogical experiment, it was possible to increase the effectiveness of the system of sports training for athletes of the Uzbekistan national team in athletics of the sport of people with musculoskeletal disorders in preparation for important competitions by optimizing and individualizing the means and methods of physical,

technical, technical design, tactical, theoretical, as well as through the use of informative indicators of the control system. During the training process, the principles of accounting and leveling of nosological features were implemented.

Practical suggestions: Sports training in the studied disciplines has a cyclical periodization. When preparing highly qualified athletes, it is most expedient to use an annual cycle, a semi-annual and a double annual macrocycle. Thus, to assess the level of physical fitness, it is necessary to use a set of pedagogical tests, individual for each discipline, each sports functional class and having a high correlation with the results in the main competitive exercise. To control technical readiness, it is advisable to use methods for determining biomechanical characteristics based on the use of biomechanical analysis, video recording of the technique of performing a competitive exercise.

To assess the functional state, it is advisable to use the means of functional control - heart rate variability; and / or means of biochemical control for such indicators as the level of concentration of urea in blood serum, the level of concentration of total protein in blood serum, the level of concentration of lactate in blood serum. To control the psychological state of athletes in Paralympic sports, it is advisable to use the method of gas discharge visualization. To improve the efficiency of the sports training system at each stage of preparation for responsible sports forums, it is necessary to include specialists from the complex group of scientific and methodological support in work with athletes who are able to work with athletes in the following areas: control and optimization of training plans, control and optimization of technical training, pedagogical control of the level of preparedness, functional control, control and optimization of psychological preparedness for training and competitive activities, increasing the level of self-regulation.

REFERENCES

1. Dilshod Baxtiyorovich Baxtiyorov AMPUNTANT FUTBOLCHILARNI JISMONIY TARBIYA VOSITALARI VA USLUBIYATI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ampuntant-futbolchilarni-jismoniy-tarbiya-vositalari-va-uslubiyati> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022).
2. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022)
3. M. X. Mirjamolov, R. F. Odilov, N. Y. Valiyeva, D. B. Baxtiyorov KO'RISH QOBILYATIDA NUQSONI BO'LGAN TALABALARDA HARAKAT KOORDINATSIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH USLUBIYATI // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №12. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ko-rish-qobilyatida-nuqsoni-bo-lgan-talabalarda-harakat-koordinatsiyasini-rivojlantirish-uslubiyati> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022)
4. М. Х. Миржамолов, Р. Ф. Одилов, Н. Ю. Валиева, Д. Б. Бахтиёров МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ КООРДИНАЦИИ ДВИЖЕНИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ С НАРУШЕНИЯМИ ЗРЕНИЯ // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/metodika-razvitiya-koordinatsii-dvizheniy-u-studentov-s-narusheniyami-zreniya> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022).
5. Kh. M. M., Svetlichnaya N. K., Abdiev Sh. A., Davlatova LT, Sobirova LB Improving Pedagogical Mechanisms to Increase Special Physical Preparation of Students with

- Disabilities in Uzbekistan //Psychology and education. – 2021. – Т. 58. – №. 2. – С. 1379-1389
6. Lola Tilapovna Davlatova JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORTDA SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH TEXNOLOGIYALARINING DOLZARBLIGI VA AHAMIYATI // Scientific progress. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/jismoniy-tarbiya-va-sportda-sog-lomlashtirish-technologieyalarining-dolzarbligi-va-ahamiyati> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022)
 7. Л. Б. Собирова КЎРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИ БУЗИЛГАН БОЛАЛАРНИ SPORT ФАОЛИЯТИ ШАРОИТЛАРИГА МОСЛАШИШ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-rish-obiliyati-buzilgan-bolalarni-sport-faoliyati-sharoitlariga-moslashish-hususiyatlari> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022).
 8. Шерали Хошимович Гофуров, Баходир Хошимович Гофуров ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА 5X5 ФУТБОЛ СПОРТ ТУРИНИ ОММАЛАШТИРИШ ОРҚАЛИ КЎРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИДА НУҚСОНИ БОР ШАХСЛАР ҲАРАКАТ ФАОЛЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zbekistonda-5x5-futbol-sport-turini-ommalashtirish-or-ali-k-rish-obiliyatida-nu-soni-bor-shahslar-arakat-faolligini-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022)
 9. Sherali Xoshimovich G'Ofurov, Bahodir Xoshimovich G'Ofurov NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA POG'ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIYASI // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/nogironlar-aravachasidan-foydalanadigan-umurtqa-pog-onasi-shikastlangan-yoshlarning-adaptiv-jismoniy-tarbiyasi> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022).
 10. Юнусов С.А. РОЛЬ И ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ ПАРАЛИМПИЙЦЕВ ПАУЭРЛИФТЁРОВ ВЫСОКОЙ КВАЛИФИКАЦИИ // Fan-Sportga. 2020. №3. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rol-i-znachimost-psihologicheskoy-podgotovki-paralimpiytsev-pauerliftyorov-vysokoy-kvalifikatsii> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022).
 11. Юнусов, С. А. "Физическое воспитание школьников в инклюзивном образовании" SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS." Scientific Journal ISSN (2021): 2181-1601
 12. Charos Alisher Qizi Berdiyeva JISMONIY IMKONIYATI CHEKLANGAN TALABA QIZLARDA EGILUVCHANLIK VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISH USULIYATI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/jismoniy-imkoniyati-cheklangan-talaba-qizlarda-egiluvchanlik-va-uni-rivojlantirish-usuliyati> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022).
 13. Рухиддин 2, [13.12.2022 11:28]
 14. Ч. А. Бердиева ЖИСМОНИЙ ИМКОНИЯТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН ТАЛАБАЛАР ОРГАНИЗМИНИНГ ФУНКЦИОНАЛ ҲОЛАТИНИ БАҲОЛАШ УСУЛИ // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №Special Issue 1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zhismoniy-imkoniyati-cheklangan-talabalar-organizmining-funksional-olatini-ba-olash-usuli> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022)
 15. Абдиев Ш.А. ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ЮҚОРИ МАЛАКАЛИ ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАРНИ МУСОБАҚА ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ РЕЖАЛАШТИРИШ // Fan-Sportga. 2020. №7. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparati-shikastlangan-yu-ori-malakali-engil-atletikachilarni-musoba-a-yuklamalarini-rezhalashtirish> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022).

16. Абдиев Ш.А. ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ЮҚОРИ МАЛАКАЛИ УЛОҚТИРУВЧИЛАРНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ МЕЪЁРЛАШ // Fan-Sportga. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparati-shikastlangan-yu-ori-malakali-ulo-tiruvchilarni-mash-ulot-yuklamalarini-meyorlash> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022)
17. Lola Tilopovna Davlatova ADAPTIV SPORT O‘YINLARINI (VOLEYBOL) O‘QITISH METODIKASIDA HARAKAT USLUBLARI VA QOIDALARI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/adaptiv-sport-oyinlarini-volleybol-o-qitish-metodikasida-harakat-uslublari-va-qoidalari> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022).
18. Миржамолов М.Х. ПАРА-СПОРТЧИЛАРНИНГ КИНЕМАТИК ҲАРАКАТ ИМКОНИАТЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ // Fan-Sportga. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/para-sportchilarning-kinematik-arakat-imkoniyatlari-talili> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022)
19. Бобомуродов, Н. Ш. "Структуры физической подготовленности курашистов" Вестник" науки и образования научно-методической журнал № 4 (82)." Часть 2.2020 (2020): 41-44
20. Бобомуродов, Н. Ш. "Features of development of physical qualities in the process of sports training of students." International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation 24.09 (2020): 4225-4229.
21. Светличная Н. Коррекционно-педагогическое воздействие на сенсомоторное развитие детей с нарушениями интеллектуального развития // Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 379-386.
22. Светличная Н.К. Развитие инклюзивного образования в области адаптивного физического воспитания детей // Вестник Тамбовского университета. Серия: Гуманитарные науки. – 2022. – Т. 27. – № 3. – С. 705-713. – DOI 10.20310/1810-0201-2022-27-3-705-713. ISSN: 1810-0201 (Print). ISSN: 2782-5825 (Online).
23. «Олимпийский спорт и спорт для всех. – 2021. – С. 412-414.
24. Валиева Н. Ю., Одилов Р. Ф. МЕТОДЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЭФФЕКТА ТОНУСНЫХ РЕФЛЕКСОВ ПРИ ДЕТСКОМ ЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНОМ ПАРАЛИЧЕ С ПОМОЩЬЮ ФИТБОЛЬНОЙ ГИМНАСТИКИ //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 966-972.
25. Odilov R.F., Valiyeva N.Y.Q. Sensor tizimida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar mashg'ulotlarini kompleks nazorat qilish //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 8. – С. 670-674.
26. Миржамолов М. Х., Одилов Р. Ф., Зокиров Д. Р. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ СТУДЕНТОВ С ОГРАНИЧЕННЫМИ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЯМИ ЗДОРОВЬЯ //Актуальные проблемы физической культуры и спорта. – 2020. – С. 20-23.
27. Миржамолов М. Х. ЭШИТИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИ РИВОЖЛАНМАГАН ЎҚУВЧИЛАРДА ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАРБИЯ МАШҒУЛОТЛАРИНИ ЎТКАЗИШ УСЛУБИЯТИ //Scientific progress. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 214-221.
28. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov MALAKALI SPRINTERCHILARNING SPORT MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/malakali-sprinterchilarning-sport-mashg-ulotlarini-rivojlantirishning-usullari> (дата обращения: 13.12.2022).
29. Еофуров Ш. Jismoniy tarbiya vositalari orqali sportchilarni o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish qobiliyatlarini shakllantirish. – 2020.

30. 28. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgachayoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 13.12.2022).
31. 29. Л. Т. Давлатова БОЛАЛАР ЦЕРЕБРАЛ ФАЛАЖИДА ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИКНИ МАШГУЛОТ ЖАРАЁНИДА ВА ИЛМИЙ НАЗАРИЙ СОҲАДА РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №Special Issue URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bolalar-tserebral-falazhida-zhismoniy-tayyorgarlikni-mash-ulot-zharayonida-va-ilmiy-nazariy-so-ada-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 12.01.2022).
32. 30. Л. Б. Собирова Эффективность использования специальных упражнений в профилактике нарушений роста у младших школьников // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №5.
33. 31. Sherali Hoshimovich G. Ofurov Qisqa masofaga yuguruvchi sportchilarni mashg'ulotlarini rivojlantirishning usullari //Scientific progress. – 2021. – №. 8.
34. 32. ЖИСМОНИЙ Л., НАЗАРИЙ Т., РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ С. Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. № Special Issue 1 //URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bolalar-tserebral-falazhida-zhismoniy-tayyorgarlikni-mash-ulot-zharayonida-va-ilmiy-nazariy-so-ada-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 12.01.2022).
35. 33. BOLALAR V. A. O'smirlar SPOR MAKTABLARIDA SPORCHILAR TAYYORLANISHINI TAKILISH BOSHLANGAN MASHG'ULOT GURUHI GofurovSh //X. Fan-Sportga. – 2020. – №. 5. – С. 38-40.
36. 34. Еофуров Ш. NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA ROG'ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIYASI //МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКАЯ ОНЛАЙН КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ. – 2021. – Т. 4. – С. 24.
37. 35. ЕОФУРОВ Ш. МАКТАБЛАРИДА БОШЛАНЕИЧ ТАЙЁРЛОВ ГУРУ^ ИДА ШУЕУЛЛАНУВЧИ ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАР МАШЕУЛОТЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ. – 2020.
38. 36. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O. MALAKALI SPRINTERCHILARNING SPORT MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – №. 4.
39. 37. Мехриддин Хайриддинович Миржамолов КЎРИШ ИМКОНИАТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН ШАХСЛАРДА СПОРТ ТЕХНИКАСИГА ЎРГАТИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ЖИҲАТЛАРИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-rish-imbkoniyati-cheklangan-shahslarda-sport-tehnikasiga-rgatishning-ziga-hos-zhi-atlari> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
40. 38. Lola Tilopovna Davlatova ADAPTIV SPORT O'YINLARINI (VOLEYBOL) O'QITISH METODIKASIDA HARAKAT USLUBLARI VA QOIDALARI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/adaptiv-sport-o-yinlarini-volleybol-o-qitish-metodikasida-harakat-uslublari-va-qoidalari> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
41. 39. Lola Tilapovna Davlatova JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORTDA SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH TEXNOLOGIYALARINING DOLZARBLIGI VA AHAMIYATI // Scientific progress. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/jismoniy-tarbiya-va-sportda-sog-lomlashtirish-texnologiyalarining-dolzarbligi-va-ahamiyati> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

42. 40. Л. Т. Давлатова БОЛАЛАР ЦЕРЕБРАЛ ФАЛАЖИДА ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИКНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЖАРАЁНИДА ВА ИЛМИЙ НАЗАРИЙ СОҲАДА РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №Special Issue 1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bolalar-tserebral-falazhida-zhismoniy-tayyorgarlikni-mash-ulot-zharayonida-va-ilmiy-nazariy-so-ada-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
43. 41. Юнусов С. А. Особенности периодизации тренировочного процесса атлетов высококвалифицированных парапауэрлифтёров. – 2021.
44. 42. Юнусов С.А. РОЛЬ И ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ ПАРАЛИМПИЙЦЕВ ПАУЭРЛИФТЁРОВ ВЫСОКОЙ КВАЛИФИКАЦИИ // Fan-Sportga. 2020. №3. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rol-i-znachimost-psihologicheskoy-podgotovki-paralimpiytsev-pauerliftyorov-vysokoy-kvalifikatsii> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
45. 43. Миразимова Ф., Давлатова Л. Т. Использование адаптивной физической культуры при обучении студентов с инвалидностью и особыми физическими потребностями //Проблеми і перспективи розвитку спортивних ігор і єдиноборств у вищих навчальних закладах. – 2022. – Т. 1. – С. 138-141.
46. Lola Tilarovna Davlatova JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORTDA SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH TEXNOLOGIYALARINING DOLZARBLIGI VA AHAMIYATI // Scientific progress. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/jismoniy-tarbiya-va-sportda-sog-lomlashtirish-technologieyalarining-dolzarlighi-va-ahamiyati> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
47. Л. Б.Собирова ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫХ УПРАЖНЕНИЙ В ПРОФИЛАКТИКЕ НАРУШЕНИЙ РОСТА У МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №5. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/effektivnost-ispolzovaniya-spetsialnyh-uprazhneniy-v-profilaktike-narusheniy-rosta-u-mladshih-shkolnikov> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
48. Kh M. M., Svetlichnaya N. K. Abdiev Sh. A., Davlatova LT, Sobirova LB Improving Pedagogical Mechanisms to Increase Special Physical Preparation of Students with Disabilities in Uzbekistan //Psychology and education. – 2021. – Т. 58. – №. 2. – С. 1379-1389.
49. Nurullayevna B. S., Sobirova L. МАКТАВГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA YASSI OYOQLIKNI JISMONIY MASHG'ULOTLARDA GIMNASTIKA VOSITALARI ORQALI OLDINI OLIISH //TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 65-69.
50. Лайло Бахромовна Собирова ГОЛБОЛ-КЎРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИ БУЗИЛГАН БОЛАЛАРНИНГ КОРДИНАЦИОН ҚОБИЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ВОСИТАЛАРИ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/golbol-k-rish-obiliyati-buzilgan-bolalarning-kordinatsion-obiliyatini-rivozhlantirish-vositalari-samaradorligi> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
51. Sobirova L. B. Efficiency of Using Special Exercises for Preventing Scoliosis Initial Age Children //Eastern European Scientific Journal. – 2018. – №. 6.
52. Sobirova L. B. THE USE PHYSICAL EDUCATION ARRANGEMENT TO PREVENT DISORDERS IN 7-10 GRADE PUPILS //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2020. – №. 3. – С. 411-415.
53. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O. et al. Scientific progress. 2022. № 1 //URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 04.02. 2022).

54. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
55. М. Х. Миржамолов, Р. Ф. Одилов, Н. Ю. Валиева, Д. Б. Бахтиёрв МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ КООРДИНАЦИИ ДВИЖЕНИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ С НАРУШЕНИЯМИ ЗРЕНИЯ // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/metodika-razvitiya-koordinatsii-dvizheniy-u-studentov-s-narusheniyami-zreniya> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
56. herali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
57. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O., Dilshod Baxtiyor O. G., Li Baxtiyorov U. A. S. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni yengil atletika mashqlari orqali mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etish //Scientific progress. – 2022. – №. 1.
58. Dilshod Baxtiyorovich Baxtiyorov AMPUNTANT FUTBOLCHILARNI JISMONIY TARBIYA VOSITALARI VA USLUBIYATI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ampuntant-futbolchilarni-jismoniy-tarbiya-vositalari-va-uslubiyati> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
59. Абдурахимова Ш. А., Бахтиеров Д. Б. МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ СИЛОВЫХ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ У ЮНЫХ СТРЕЛКОВ 13-14 ЛЕТ И ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СПОРТИВНОГО МАСТЕРСТВА //Рекомендовано к изданию Советом по качеству УралГУФК Протокол № 8 от 14 мая 2018 г. – 2018. – С. 19.
60. Абдиев Ш.А. ПЛАНИРОВАНИЕ ТРЕНИРОВОЧНОЙ НАГРУЗКИ ВЫСОКОКВАЛИФИЦИРОВАННЫХ ЛЕГКОАТЛЕТОВ С ПОРАЖЕНИЕМ ОПОРНО-ДВИГАТЕЛЬНОГО АППАРАТА // Современное образование (Узбекистан). 2021. №1 (98). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/planirovanie-trenirovochnoy-nagruzki-vysokokvalifitsirovannyh-legkoatletov-s-porazhenim-oporno-dvigatelno-go-apparata-1> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022).
61. Абдиев Ш.А. ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ЮҚОРИ МАЛАКАЛИ ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАРНИ МУСОБАҚА ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ РЕЖАЛАШТИРИШ // Fan-Sportga. 2020. №7. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparati-shikastlangan-yu-ori-malakali-engil-atletikachilarni-musoba-a-yuklamalarini-rezhalashtirish> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022).
62. Абдиев Ш.А. ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ЮҚОРИ МАЛАКАЛИ УЛОҚТИРУВЧИЛАРНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ МЕЪЁРЛАШ // Fan-Sportga. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparati-shikastlangan-yu-ori-malakali-ulo-tiruvchilarni-mash-ulot-yuklamalarini-meyorlash> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022).
63. Шерзод Абдурахмонович Абдиев ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИДА НУҚСОНИ БЎЛГАН ЮҚОРИ МАЛАКАЛИ УЛОҚТИРУВЧИЛАРНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ ОПТИМАЛЛАШТИРИШ // Scientific progress. 2022. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparatida-nu-soni-b-lgan-yu-ori>

- malakali-ulo-tiruvchilarni-mash-ulot-yuklamalarini-optimallashtirish (дата обращения: 11.11.2022).
64. Шерзод Абдурахмонович Абдиев ПЛАНИРОВАНИЕ ТРЕНИРОВОЧНОЙ НАГРУЗКИ ВЫСОКОКВАЛИФИЦИРОВАННЫХ ЛЕГКОАТЛЕТОВ С ПОРАЖЕНИЕМ ОПОРНО-ДВИГАТЕЛЬНОГО АППАРАТА // Academic research in educational sciences. 2020. №3. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/planirovanie-trenirovochnoy-nagruzki-vysokokvalifitsirovannyh-legkoatletov-s-porazhenim-oporno-dvigatelno-go-apparata> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022).
65. Абдиев Ш.А. Енгил атлетикани ўқитиш методикаси (Адаптив жисмоний тарбия ва спорт) // Ўқув қўлланма- Чирчиқ, Т.; 2020. - 200 б.
66. Миржамолов.М.Х., Абдиев Ш.А. Improving Pedagogical Mechanisms to Increase Special Physical Preparation of Students with Disabilities in Uzbekistan.(2021) 58 (2) ISSN:00333077. 317 - 323 Pg.
67. М. Х. Миржамолов, Ч. А. Бердиева ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ТАЛАБАЛАРДА СКИБИНСК ИНДЕКСИ БЎЙИЧА ЎРТА АРИФМЕТИК ҚИЙМАТЛАР // Scientific progress. 2022. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparati-shikastlangan-talabalarda-skibinsk-indeksi-b-yicha-rta-arifmetik-iymatlar> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
68. Миржамолов М. Х., Одилов Р. Ф., Валиева Н. Ю. ДБ Бахтиёров МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ КООРДИНАЦИИ ДВИЖЕНИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ С НАРУШЕНИЯМИ ЗРЕНИЯ //Scientific progress. – 2022. – №. 1.
69. Миржамолов М.Х. РИО-ДЕ ЖАНЕЙРО ШАХРИДА БЎЛИБ ЎТГАН XV ВА ТОКИОДА БЎЛИБ ЎТГАН XVI ПАРАЛИМПИАДА ЎЙИНЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ // Fan-Sportga. 2021. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rio-de-zhaneyro-sha-rida-b-lib-tgan-xv-va-tokioda-b-lib-tgan-xvi-paralimpiya-yinlari-ta-lili> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
70. Миржамолов М. Х. Жисмоний имконияти чекланган уқувчи-ларнинг спорт машрулотларига мослашиши //У^ ув услубий мажмуа, Тошкент. – 2014.
71. М. Х. Миржамолов, Р. Ф. Одилов, Н. Ю. Валиева, Д. Б. Бахтиёров МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ КООРДИНАЦИИ ДВИЖЕНИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ С НАРУШЕНИЯМИ ЗРЕНИЯ // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/metodika-razvitiya-koordinatsii-dvizheniy-u-studentov-s-parusheniyami-zreniya> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
72. Salomov R. S., Mirjamolov M. X. Adaptation of students with disabilities to sports is a teaching aid. – 2015.
73. Мехриддин Хайриддинович Миржамолов КЎРИШ ИМКОНИЯТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН ШАХСЛАРДА СПОРТ ТЕХНИКАСИГА ЎРГАТИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ЖИҲАТЛАРИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-rish-imkoniyati-cheklangan-shahslarda-sport-tehnikasiga-rgatishning-ziga-hos-zhi-atlari> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
74. Миржамолов М.Х. ПАРА-СПОРТЧИЛАРНИНГ КИНЕМАТИК ҲАРАКАТ ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ // Fan-Sportga. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/para-sportchilarning-kinematik-arakat-imkoniyatlari-ta-lili> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
75. М. Х. Миржамолов, Ч. А. Бердиева ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ТАЛАБАЛАРДА СКИБИНСК ИНДЕКСИ БЎЙИЧА ЎРТА АРИФМЕТИК ҚИЙМАТЛАР // Scientific progress. 2022. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparati-shikastlangan-talabalarda-skibinsk-indeksi-b-yicha-rta-arifmetik-iymatlar> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

76. Миржамолов М.Х. ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ПАРАЛИМПИЯ ҲАРАКАТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ВА ЗАХИРА СПОРТЧИЛАРНИ ТАЙЁРЛАШДА ИЛМИЙ ЁНДАШУВ // Fan-Sportga. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zbekistonda-paralimpiya-arakatini-rivozhlantirish-va-zahira-sportchilarni-tayyorlashda-ilmiy-yondashuv> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
77. . Х. Миржамолов ТАЯНЧ – ҲАРАКАТ АЪЗОЛАРИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ЎҚУВЧИЛАРДА МУСКУЛ ФАОЛИЯТИНИНГ БУЗИЛИШ ТАРТИБИ УЧУН ФУНКЦИОНАЛ ТИЗИМ ДИНАМИКАСИ // Scientific progress. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-azolari-shikastlangan-uvchilarda-muskul-faoliyatining-buzilish-tartibi-uchun-funksional-tizim-dinamikasi> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
78. ПАРА-СПОРТЧИЛАРНИНГ КИНЕМАТИК ҲАРАКАТ ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ Миржамолов М.Х. Фан-Спортга. 2022. № 2. С. 8-10.
79. Миржамолов М. Х. ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ, УЧАЩИХСЯ С ОГРАНИЧЕННЫМИ ФИЗИЧЕСКИМИ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЯМИ //Актуальные проблемы физической культуры и спорта. – 2019. – С. 50-55.
80. Миржамолов М. Х. Болалар мия фалажида тонус рефлексларининг таъсирини фитбол1 гимнастикаси ёрдамида ривожлантириш услубияти // Современное образование (Узбекистан). 2017. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bolalar-miya-falazhida-tonus-reflekslarining-tasirini-fitbol1-gimnastikasi-yordamida-rivozhlantirish-uslubiyati> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
81. Mirjamolov M. H. Evaluating Results of Functional Opportunities and Organism Systems Relationship of Students with Limited Physical Opportunity //www. auris-verlag. de. – 2017. – Т. 4. – С. 5.
82. Hayriddinovich M. M. THE RESULT OF THE MARKS OF MUTUAL DEPENDENCE BODY SYSTEM OF THE STUDENT'S WHOSE PHISICAL POSSIBILITY ARE LIMITED AND FUNCTIONAL CAPACITY //ББК 75.03 А 38. – С. 142.
83. Мехриддин Хайриддинович Миржамолов КЎРИШ ИМКОНИЯТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН ШАХСЛАРДА СПОРТ ТЕХНИКАСИГА ЎРГАТИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ЖИҲАТЛАРИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-rish-imkoniyati-cheklangan-shahslarda-sport-tehnikasiga-rgatishning-ziga-hos-zhi-atlari> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
84. Бобомуродов Н. Ш. Физическая реабилитация борцов с нарушениями в позвоночнике у квалифицированных борцов //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 874-879.
85. Бобомуродов Н. Ш. Technique of Recording Technical and Tactical Actions in Fight Turon //Eastern European Scientific Journal. – 2018. – №. 4. – С. 16-19.
86. Бобомуродов Н. Ш. Юкори малакали курашчиларнинг техник-тактик харакатларини ривожлантириш методикаси //Педагогик таълим" Илмий-назарий журнал. Тошкент. – 2011.
87. Бобомуродов Н. Ш. Контроль и анализ действий в борьбе турон //Фан-спортга" илмий-назарий журналы. Тошкент. – 2011.
88. Бобомуродов Н. Ш. Физиологический подход в прогнозировании перспективности борцов-туронистов //МуРаллим х, ем узликсиз билимлендириу" илмий-методикалык журнал. Нукус.-2019. – 2019.
89. Миржамолов М. Х., Одилов Р. Ф., Зокиров Д. Р. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ СТУДЕНТОВ С ОГРАНИЧЕННЫМИ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЯМИ ЗДОРОВЬЯ //Актуальные проблемы физической культуры и спорта. – 2020. – С. 20-23.

90. Светличная Н.К. Адаптивное и оздоровительное физическое воспитание: учебное пособие. – Ташкент: O'ZKITOBSAVDONASHRIYOTI, 2022. – 200 с. ISBN: 978-9943-7751-1-4.
91. Светличная Н.К. Спорт в период пандемии COVID-19 // Фан-Спортга. – 2022. – № 1. – С. 3-7. ISSN: 2181-7804.
92. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/sport-v-period-pandemii-covid-19>
93. Светличная Н.К. Развитие инклюзивного образования в области адаптивного физического воспитания детей // Вестник Тамбовского университета. Серия: Гуманитарные науки. – 2022. – Т. 27. – № 3. – С. 705-713. – DOI 10.20310/1810-0201-2022-27-3-705-713. ISSN: 1810-0201 (Print). ISSN: 2782-5825 (Online).
94. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/razvitiye-inklyuzivnogo-obrazovaniya-v-oblasti-adaptivnogo-fizicheskogo-vospitaniya-detey>
95. Светличная Н. Коррекционно-педагогическое воздействие на сенсомоторное развитие детей с нарушениями интеллектуального развития // Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 379-386. ISSN: 2181-1385.
96. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/korrektsionno-pedagogicheskoe-vozdeystvie-na-sensomotornoe-razvitiye-detey-s-narusheniyami-intellektualnogo-razvitiya>
97. Светличная Н.К. Комплексный подход в оценке функционального состояния лиц, занимающихся физической культурой и спортом // Вестник Ташкентской медицинской академии, 2022. Специальный выпуск. – С.385-388. ISSN: 2181-7812.
98. Светличная Н.К. Odamning jismoniy va funktsional tayyorgarligi darajisini baholash usuli. Способ оценки уровня физической и функциональной подготовленности человека: Ixtiro patenti № IAP 07017 // Rasmiy axborotnoma, №8(256), 2022. – С.48-49.
99. URL: https://my.ima.uz/cert-v1/default/check-patent?check_id=9824c26e1b6bd0951e0392ad4108657a
100. Светличная Н.К. Интеграция в спортивном образовании Узбекистана // Актуальные проблемы адаптивной физической культуры: материалы Всероссийской научно-практической конференции с международным участием. – Омск: СибГУФКС, 2022. – С. 198-204. ISBN: 978-5-91930-207-0.
101. Theoretical analysis of motor activity in assessing the mass sports movement of schoolchildren // Eurasian Journal of Sport Science. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 1-4
102. Умумий ўрта таълим мактабларида ўқувчиларни жисмоний тарбия ва оммавий спортга жалб қилишда мусобақаларнинг ўрни // Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 9/S. – С. 21-27.
103. ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ МАССОВОЙ СПОРТИВНО-ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНОЙ РАБОТЫ В ОБЩЕОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ШКОЛАХ // Fan-Sportga. – 2018. – №. 1. – С. 11-15.
104. Светличная Н.К. Спорт и двигательная активность в период пандемии // Сборник Международной научной конференции «Итоги XXXII летних Олимпийских, XVI Паралимпийских Игр 2021 года и вопросы подготовки к очередным Олимпийским и Паралимпийским играм». – Чирчик: УзГУФКС, 2022. – С.140-142.